

CLINICOPATHOLOGICAL CONFERENCE: MILIARY TUBERCULOSIS AND PANCYTOPENIA IN AN ELDERLY MAN

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Case Report

A 81-year-old man was admitted as an emergency for chest infection and anaemia to the Department of Geriatrics of the Princess Margaret Hospital on 11.6.1993. He complained of dizziness, malaise and weakness for two weeks. For the past ten days, he experienced chills, cough productive of whitish sputum, anorexia, as well as retrosternal and epigastric discomfort. He slipped and fell on the day before admission. He was a retired ferry sailor, living alone and was financially supported by his sons. He was an ex-smoker, and there was no known exposure to silica or tuberculosis.

He had been followed up in a chest clinic yearly, but he had no history of active tuberculosis. Three years ago, he had an oesophago-gastro-duodenoscopy for epigastric discomfort but he was unaware of the diagnosis. He had history of a benign tumour over his right hip with excision done. He had been hospitalized in another hospital in July 1989 for loss of consciousness at home for two hours and was suspected to have convulsion, but a computerized tomography (CT) of brain then was normal.

On admission, his temperature was 36.6°C, blood pressure 150/90 mmHg, pulse 80/min, respiratory rate 24/min, and body weight 41.5kg. He was thin and pale. He had no jaundice or lymphadenopathy. His chest was clear. There were no heart murmurs. No abdominal masses were palpable, and per-rectal examination was normal. He was alert and orientated. Cataract was present on the left eye, and the optic fundi were normal. There was generalized muscular weakness, and assistance was required for transfer and walking. He expectorated greenish sputum. The admission chest film (Figure 1a), which was overpenetrated, revealed bilateral fibrotic upper zone with blunted right costophrenic angle suggesting old tuberculosis. The electrocardiogram was normal. Swinging fever up 39.5°C, with peaks at 4am, was recorded (Figure 2: a).

Initial investigations (Fig. 3) revealed normochromic

normocytic anaemia, leucopenia, high ESR (81mm/hr), hypoalbuminaemia (30g/l) and raised alkaline phosphatase of liver origin (362iu/l). His renal function test was normal. Urine examination showed no protein or glucose, a few white blood cells, and the bacterial count was less than 10^4 organism/ml. The plasma glucose was 6.0mmol/l.

He was treated initially as chest infection. However, fever persisted after 18 days of antibiotics treatment, which included amoxycillin, cefuroxime, aztreonam, cefotaxime, and metronidazole. He remained weak, anorexic and he developed bilateral ankle oedema. Blood tests two weeks after admission (Figure 3) revealed pancytopenia (Hb 5.6g/dl, WCC $2.1 \times 10^9/l$, platelet $111 \times 10^9/l$), worsened hypoalbuminaemia (22g/l), rising serum urea (8.9mmol/l) and creatinine (137umol/l). The tuberculin test was negative. Cultures taken from blood, urine and bone marrow grew no organisms. Sputum for acid-fast bacilli (AFB) was ordered, but no sputum samples were collected. Bone marrow smear for AFB was negative. Blood for malaria and monospot test were negative. HBsAg was negative and anti-HBs was positive. Immunoglobulin pattern revealed low concentration of immunoglobulin M at 0.43g/l (reference: 0.63-3.07).

He was investigated for anaemia and pancytopenia. The peripheral blood smear showed poikilocytosis, anisocytosis, moderate number of elliptocytes, left shift of neutrophils and slightly reduced platelets. The reticulocyte count was 1.0%. Fe and total iron binding capacity (TIBC) were reduced at 7.5umol/l and 19.8umol/l respectively, while the serum ferritin was raised at 1810pmol/l (reference 42-1100). Stool for occult blood was negative. Oesophago-gastro-duodenoscopy revealed minimal gastritis. Serum B12 was normal at 178pmol/l (reference 150-700). Serum and red blood cell folate were normal. Bone marrow trephine biopsy on 17.6.1993 showed hypoplasia with trilineage reduction and iron deficiency, but no granulomatous lesion. He was transfused two pints of

Figure 1a. Chest radiograph on admission 11.6.1993, showing bilateral fibrotic upper zone and blunted right costophrenic angle.

Figure 1b. Chest radiograph on 3.7.1993 showing miliary nodules.

Figure 1c. Chest radiograph on 26.7.1993 showing deterioration, with upper zone consolidations and bilateral hilar enlargement.

Figure 1d. Chest radiograph on 5.8.1993 showing subsequent improvement.

Figure 3. Haematological changes (top), antituberculous chemotherapy (middle) and biochemical changes (bottom) 11.6.1993 - 31.3.1994.

Figure 4a. Ultrasound of right kidney showing increase in renal echogenicity and multiple cysts (arrows).

Figure 4b. Ultrasound of left kidney showing increase in renal echogenicity and a large cyst (arrow).

six pints of packed cells; two pints each on 24.6.1993, 8.7.1993 and 25.7.1993 respectively.

There was recrudescence of fever from 22.7.1993 onwards (Figure 2: e). A repeat chest film on 26.7.1993 (Figure 1c) revealed deterioration compared with previous films, with areas of consolidation over both upper zones and bilateral hilar enlargement. However, he remained well, was not dyspnoeic, and was gaining weight. He was reassessed by chest physician on 27.7.1993, and rifampicin 300mg was reintroduced in view of the apparent deterioration in the chest film. The fever finally subsided one month after the antituberculous treatment (Figure 2: f). A repeat chest film on 5.8.1993 (Figure 1d) showed improvement compared with the previous film.

On 2.8.1993, he complained of skin discoloration over his forearms and legs. Examination revealed fresh purpura over the extensor aspects (Figure 5a). His platelet count then was only $67 \times 10^9/l$, which had dropped from $123 \times 10^9/l$. This drop in platelet count was attributed to the dilutional effect of blood transfusion given on 25.7.1993;

similar drops were observed in previous transfusions (Figure 3). In addition, erythematous skin nodules, 3mm-5mm in diameter, were noted over the posterior aspect of legs and thighs, especially on the right side (Figures 5a, 5b). The patient claimed that the skin nodules had been there for two years. Skin biopsy of these nodules on 4.8.1993 showed evidence of mycobacterial infection (Figures 6a, 6b); there were marked granulomatous inflammation and focal necrosis in the deep dermis and subcutis. Langhan type giant cells were also seen. Ziehl-Neelsen stain for acid-fast bacilli was positive (Figure 6b inset). Part of the skin biopsy specimen was sent for AFB smear and culture; both returned later as negative.

He was transferred to another hospital for further rehabilitation on 12.8.1993. At the time of transfer, his body weight was 43.5kg, a gain in 2kg, but he was still pancytopenic. He was further transfused with five pints of blood, one pint on 16.8.1993, two pints each on 24.8.1993 and 28.9.1993. A bone marrow aspirate on 5.10.1993 showed scanty hypocellular flakes with suppressed erythropoiesis (normoblastic), granulopoiesis and thrombopoiesis, but no evidence of haematological malignancy. He was discharged on 16.10.1993.

On 22.10.1993, a result was returned that one of the three urine specimens taken on 8.7.1993 grew *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* sensitive to isoniazid, rifampicin, ethambutol, streptomycin; the other two specimens were negative. No *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* was cultured from bone marrow specimens.

He complained of right hip pain when followed up at the geriatric out-patient clinic on 3.11.1993. X-ray of the right hip revealed no abnormality. When seen again on 1.12.1993, the right hip pain persisted, especially on climbing upstairs. He volunteered a history of fall in toilet in mid-September 1993 during hospitalization, and he afterwards noticed dull-aching pain over the lateral aspect of the right side of his buttock, especially after prolonged lying on the right. Examination of his right hip revealed localized tenderness over the greater trochanter without any swelling, and the range of movement was full. A 5cm surgical scar over the right hip was noted. Specific questioning about the operation and tracing his medical follow-up cards revealed the following history from the patient with the help of his son.

The patient was unwell since 1989, complaining of frequent headache and blurred vision. In 1990, he was seen irregularly at the general out-patient clinic for on-and-off malaise and dizziness. In early 1991 he noticed a painless skin nodule over his right thigh, initially the size of a green pea or the head of a match. It grew to the size of a white pea one week later. Excision was done under local anaesthesia in another hospital and he was told that it was a benign tumor, but the excision wound did not heal until one month later. In May 1991, he was referred to a chest clinic because an abnormal chest film was detected during

Figure 5a. Right leg showing skin nodules (black arrow) and purpura (white arrow).

Figure 5b. Close-up view of skin nodules.

work-up for cataract extraction. He had serial chest films checked and sputum saved for AFB. He was reassured then that he had old pulmonary tuberculosis only, and he was followed up annually since 20.2.1992. The chest radiographs taken at the chest clinic on 4.5.1991 and 3.3.1993 were traced

Figure 6a. Low power photomicrograph of skin biopsy from right calf showing necrotizing granuloma lined by epithelioid histiocytes.

Figure 6b. High power photomicrograph showing a Langhan type multinucleated giant cell (arrow). Ziehl-Neelsen stain (inset) reveals an acid-fast bacillus (arrowhead).

and retrospectively reviewed. They showed fibrotic bilateral upper zone with blunted right costo-phrenic angle, similar to the admission chest film taken on 11.6.1993. The hospital record of the admission for right thigh nodule could not be traced and the histology of that "tumor" was not available for review.

Repeat X-ray of the right hip on 1.12.1993 was reported as "cortical irregularities are noted over the greater trochanter of right femur. Suspicious lucencies are also observed. Tuberculosis infection has to be considered." The ESR was raised at 67mm/hr. Complete blood picture revealed macrocytic anaemia (Hb 9.2g/dl, MCV105fl), leucopenia (WCC $2.9 \times 10^9/l$, N65%, E2.2%, B0.7%, L21.1%, M11%) and mild thrombocytopenia. He was thus admitted again on 5.1.1994 to the Department of Geriatrics of our Hospital for suspected tuberculosis of right hip and repeat marrow biopsy for persistent pancytopenia, the differential diagnoses of which were marrow suppression by tubercu-

Figure 7. Bone marrow aspirate on 18.1.94 showing myelodysplastic changes eg. multinuclearity (arrowhead) and nuclear deformity (arrow) in erythroblasts.

losis, underlying myelodysplastic syndrome, or tuberculous ileitis with vitamin B12 deficiency.

Peripheral blood smear showed macrocytosis and anisocytosis, moderately reduced white blood cell count with normal differential distribution, and slightly reduced platelets. A bone marrow aspirate from right iliac crest on 7.1.94 revealed hypoplastic marrow, but maturation of all cell lines was normal. Bone marrow for AFB smear was negative. Serum vitamin B12 was low at 78pmol/l (reference range: 150-700) while the serum folate was normal at 13.7nmol/l (reference range: 7-39). Barium meal and follow through revealed a large duodenal diverticulum, but no ileo-caecal abnormality. Vitamin B12 1mg imi qd was started on 20.1.94, but no response was seen after one week. A repeat marrow aspirate on 18.1.94 (Figure 7) showed myelodysplastic syndrome - refractory anaemia; there were normocellular and dysplastic erythropoiesis, i.e. nuclear fragmentation and deformity, multinuclearity, intercellular bridges, markedly increase iron with occasional pathological sideroblasts. Pyridoxine was increased to 50mg tds on 28.1.1994. Immunoglobulin pattern repeated on 21.1.1994 still showed a low level of immunoglobulin M at 0.43g/l. Antibody to HIV was negative.

He was further investigated for suspected tuberculous trochanteritis. X-ray of hips on 6.1.1994 (Figure 8) was reported as "ill-defined lytic area with cortical break and new bone formation is seen in the right greater trochanter with normal hip joint. Tuberculous infection is certainly a possibility since this is not an uncommon site and the strong clinical history. Ill-defined bone loss is also noted on the left side. CT of both greater trochanters can be of use for further delineation." Bone scan using technetium 99m-MDP

on 26.1.1994 revealed increase uptake in right greater trochanter together with positive blood pool and blood flow suggesting the diagnosis of trochanteric bursitis (Figure 9a). A photon deficient lesion in left kidney is noted (Figure 9b), corresponding to the large left renal cyst detected with ultrasonogram. CT scan of hips on 3.2.1994 was reported as infection at right greater trochanter, likely due to tuberculosis: "Multiple small superficial bony erosions are noted at the lateral cortex of greater trochanter of right femur (Figure 10a). Adjacent soft tissue is swollen, with contrast enhancement (Figure 10b). A small hypodense area abutting the bony erosions is likely a small abscess." Tuberculosis of the right trochanteric bursa was thus diagnosed.

He was operated under spinal anaesthesia on 21.2.1994. Greyish infected tissue was noted at the lining of right trochanteric bursa. The periosteum over greater trochanter was involved. The infected tissue was debrided and histology of the synovium from the right trochanteric bursa was reported as granulomatous inflammation consistent with mycobacterial infection (Figure 11), though no AFB was demonstrated by Ziehl-Neelsen stain. He recovered promptly post-operatively, with reduced right hip pain, and he could walk unaided when discharged on 7.3.1994. On discharge, his Hb was 8.3g/dl, WCC $3.2 \times 10^9/l$, and platelet $166 \times 10^9/l$; and his body weight was 45kg. When followed up on 30.3.1994, his Hb rose to 9.9g/dl, WCC was $3.5 \times 10^9/l$, and platelet $154 \times 10^9/l$.

Figure 8. X-ray of right hip showing cortical break and new bone formation over greater trochanter of right hip.

Figure 9a. Bone scan showing increased uptake (arrow) in right greater trochanter suggesting trochanteric bursitis (anterior view).

Figure 9b. Bone scan showing photon deficient lesion in left kidney compatible with left renal cyst (posterior view).

Figure 10a. CT scan of hips showing superficial bony erosions at lateral cortex of greater trochanter of right femur.

Figure 10b. CT scan of hips showing swollen soft tissue adjacent to greater trochanter of right femur.

Discussion*

Miliary tuberculosis is defined as dissemination of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* resulting in widespread visceral tubercles, usually the size of millet seeds (1 to 2 mm) and frequently caesating^{1,2}. Since the 1960's, a **changing pattern of miliary tuberculosis** has been reported¹⁻¹⁵: a higher peak age incidence, insidious and non-specific presentation so that the diagnosis was often delayed⁷ or made only at necropsy^{4,5,8,16,17}, and many were misdiagnosed in

life as disseminated neoplastic diseases^{4,13-15} or simple pneumonia¹⁴. In a recent French study¹⁵, 72.5% were aged over 65 years and 32.5% were aged over 80 years. In the Edinburgh series³, the peak age incidence was in the eighth decade. This was attributed to the breakdown of old tuberculous foci in elderly patients with compromised immunity. Today, many elderly people had been infected by tuberculosis in large numbers during childhood before the establishment of tuberculosis prevention programs. Many

* Discussion of the case itself is in italics

Figure 11. Synovial biopsy from right trochanteric bursa, showing granulomatous lesion with dense lymphocytic infiltration and the presence of multinucleated giant cells (arrow).

of those who have survived are still harbouring tubercle bacilli in encapsulated lesion of primary tuberculosis complexes. Entry of tubercle bacilli into a lymphatic or blood vessel results in miliary tuberculosis^{2,9}. A recent study in Hong Kong⁵ also confirmed this pattern of miliary tuberculosis locally. Of the 15 patients with miliary tuberculosis in the Hong Kong series, 87% were aged over 50 years and 53% aged over 60 years. The non-specific presentation, the absence of typical radiological findings and the advanced stage of the illness rendered the diagnosis difficult, so that only 7 of the 15 patients were diagnosed correctly during life. The subacute form of this disease may have a very prolonged course of progressive debilitation¹⁴ not unlike that of an occult neoplasm. The more acute "septicaemic" type¹⁸ in which toxæmia may be so profound as to resemble typhoid fever, is not uncommon in Asia.

The **clinical features**, investigatory findings and outcome of six series of miliary tuberculosis reported in Edinburgh³, Stockholm⁴, Hong Kong⁵, Cape Town⁶, Baltimore² and Jiang Xi⁷ are summarized and compared in Table 1. The predominant symptoms were non-specific: fever, malaise and weight loss. Fever may be absent¹⁹, low-grade or intermittent^{3,10}. Respiratory symptoms may be absent as reported in the cryptic type in the Edinburgh³ and Hong Kong² series. Headache and abdominal pain, if present, point to the presence of tuberculosis meningitis and peritonitis respectively¹⁴.

*Our patient presented with a fall, together with fever, malaise, weakness, anorexia and cough. He was initially treated as simple pneumonia. However, there was no fever response after 18 days of antibacterial drugs and repeated cultures were negative for organisms. The importance of tuberculosis, particularly disseminated tuberculosis, as a cause of **fever of unknown origin** has been emphasized^{3,4,20-22}. In the Edinburgh series³, 63% (10/16) of cryptic miliary tuberculosis presented with fever of un-*

known origin as the diagnostic problem. Disseminated tuberculosis is one of the most common diseases presenting as fever of unknown origin in Hong Kong²². Choroidal tubercles, pathognomonic of miliary tuberculosis, were not detectable in this patient, but they are usually absent in the cryptic type^{3,10} and are rare in non-Caucasians^{5,23}. The tuberculin test in this patient was negative. It is well known that patients with miliary tuberculosis may have a negative tuberculin reaction²⁴, but some may become tuberculin positive on repeat testing^{14,24}.

The classical **miliary pattern** consists of diffuse small interstitial pulmonary nodules of soft tissue density and approximately the size of millet seeds (1 to 3mm). This X-ray pattern can occur in many conditions, but when associated with an acute febrile illness, points to three differential diagnoses¹¹: miliary tuberculosis, miliary fungal diseases²⁵, and occasionally metastatic carcinoma. Visualization of the typical miliary pattern in a chest film is dependent on the development of progressive or complicated miliary lesions². As can be seen from Table 1, the chest film was normal from 30% to 80%, and miliary mottling was present from 0% to 78% of miliary tuberculosis. Only 33.6% showed typical miliary changes on chest radiographs in a recent Jiang Xi study in China⁷.

The admission chest film (Figure 1a) of this patient showed evidence of old tuberculosis only, but a miliary pattern was detected in a repeat chest film taken three weeks later. Negative pulmonary X-ray findings contribute to the missed diagnosis in the Stockholm series⁴ and to the diagnostic problem of the cryptic cases in the series from Edinburgh³, Hong Kong⁵, and Jiang Xi⁷. It is important therefore to realize that the absence of a miliary infiltrate in admission chest radiographs does not exclude a diagnosis of miliary tuberculosis^{4,11,14} since it may appear within a few weeks^{6, 14,26} or never at all even though miliary pulmonary involvement is demonstrated at autopsy^{12,27}. Moreover, the miliary infiltrate may be atypical, with predominant reticular pattern or variable size of nodules⁶. Berger has suggested that careful inspection of an under-penetrated chest film with special attention to the intercostal spaces may reveal miliary shadows²⁶. The use of nuclear imaging of the lungs has also been reported to contribute to the early detection of miliary tuberculosis in those with normal chest radiographs²⁸.

There are three ways of **confirming the clinical impression of tuberculosis**: a positive culture, smear or histology. For patients with occult or minimal miliary disease, the amount of bacilli discharged into the sputum or other body fluids are in the range of 10² to 10⁵/ml (the number required for recovery by culture) rather than above 10⁵/ml (the number required for a positive smear)¹¹.

The difficulty with a culture is that it takes more than a month to grow. In this patient, Mycobacterium tuberculosis was cultured from the urine three months after collection. New radiometric methods of mycobacterial cul-

Table 1. Clinical features, investigatory findings and outcome of 6 series of miliary tuberculosis.

	Edinburgh (n=40)	Stockholm (n=5)	HongKong (n=15)	CapeTown (n=109)	Baltimore (n=40)	JiangXi (n=125)
Reference	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[2]	[7]
Age: range in years	21-89	20-63	16-77	13-80	25-91	0.5-71
> 60 years	58%	20%	53%		50%	
> 50 years	65%	60%	87%			
Mortality	25%	100%	80%	24%		
FUO	63% (10/16)	100%	33%		15%	
<i>Symptoms</i>						
Fever	83%	100%	73%)	30%	86%
Malaise	78%		33%) 92%	15%	
Weight loss	75%		20%)	43%	52%
Weakness					23%	52%
Anorexia					30%	60%
Respiratory	18%		27%	72%	38%	77%
Night sweats	18%		7%		18%	38%
Abdominal	13%		7%	21%		
Headache		20%	7%		10%	
Urinary	13%				10%	
<i>Signs</i>						
Hepatomegaly	20%		53%	52%		
Splenomegaly	10%		47%	15%		
Lymphadenopathy	8%	20%	0%	21%		36%
Choroidal tubercles	8%		0%	< 2%		
<i>Chest radiographs</i>						
Miliary mottling	50%	0%	0%	78% (42/54)	25% (9/36)	34%
Normal	30%	80%	33%			
"Old tuberculosis"			27%	17% (6/54)		
Pneumonia	8%		20%			
<i>Blood tests</i>						
ESR > 50mm/h	30%	80%	50% (3/6)			
Blood abnormalities	38%	40%	73%	87%		
Pancytopenia	8%		20%	6%		
Raised alkPase			53%	83%		
<i>Positive yield from specific investigations</i>						
Positive tuberculin test	80% (20/25)	50% (2/4)	0% (0/6)	43% (20/47)		54% (19/35)
Bronchoscopy				86% (44/51)		60% (3/5)
Liver biopsy	33% (1/3)		75% (3/4)	100% (10/10)		
Marrow biopsy			56% (5/9)	86% (19/22)		
Positive culture	58%		33% (4/12)	56% (62/110)		
First diagnosed at necropsy	19% (3/16)	100%	53%			

ture can shorten the time to positive cultures²⁹, but the expense will probably preclude its widespread use. For rapid diagnosis of miliary tuberculosis, biopsies of liver or bone marrow, and fiberoptic bronchoscopy have been advocated^{6,30,31}. For our patient, marrow biopsy revealed no granulomata but a positive skin biopsy provided the first confirmation of the diagnosis. **Tuberculosis of the skin as part of disseminated tuberculosis**, though rare, has been reported^{14,32-34}. It can be in the form of subcutaneous abscesses^{14,34}, subcutaneous nodules³² or miliary skin nodules³³. The patient's description of the first "benign" nodule over his right thigh corresponds to the size of a millet seed. The clinical significance of his skin nodules were however ignored for two years until the present illness. The skin nodules are restricted to his lower limbs and are more abundant over the right side. This is consistent with a lymphatic spread from a focus in the right greater trochanter.

Confirmation of the diagnosis of miliary tuberculosis may not be immediate, so much can be said for applying a **therapeutic test**^{3,9,10,13}. In the Edinburgh series, 10 out of the 16 cases of cryptic miliary tuberculosis were diagnosed by a therapeutic trial with para-aminosalicylic acid and isoniazid, a fall of temperature usually within one week, improved appetite, increased well-being, weight gain and a rise in haemoglobin being the criteria of improvement^{3,14}. The response to antituberculous drugs has been regarded as a useful diagnostic test in cases of pyrexia of unknown origin²⁰⁻²². Improvement may however be delayed and Yu⁵ has emphasized that an adequate trial of at least six weeks may be needed.

For the Edinburgh series³, treatment with antituberculous drugs (isoniazid, streptomycin, para-aminosalicylic acid) resulted in normalization of the temperature within one week for 25% (9/36). For the series of Munt¹⁴ treated with isoniazid, streptomycin and para-aminosalicylic acid, 14.3%(9/63) was afebrile within one week, and 32%(20/63) required over 30 days for a return to a normal temperature. Munt further noted that rapid temperature defervescence after appropriate antituberculous treatment was not necessarily associated with improved survival; the average duration of fever was 19.2 days in those eventually dying of miliary tuberculosis and 32.5 days in the survivors. In the Cape Town series⁶, antituberculous therapy (isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide and ethambutol or streptomycin) resulted in complete resolution of pyrexia within a median duration of 7 days (range: 1 to 55 days) and 76% were afebrile within 14 days. The prompt response in the Cape Town series may be related to the use of the bactericidal drug rifampicin.

In our patient, therapeutic trial with isoniazid and rifampicin resulted in prompt defervescence the next day, but these drugs were withdrawn after 4 days because of deteriorating liver and renal function tests. A study in Taipei has demonstrated an adverse outcome for isoniazid-rifampicin-induced hepatitis in hepatitis B car-

riers³⁵. Our patient was anti-HBs positive. Reintroduction of antituberculous chemotherapy with isoniazid, ethambutol and ofloxacin resulted in a downward trend of temperature within the first two weeks but a recrudescence of fever in the third week of treatment. Rifampicin was reintroduced at a lower dose of 300mg daily. The temperature finally returned to normal after 30 days of antituberculous chemotherapy.

The chest radiograph paradoxically deteriorated in this patient in the third week of antituberculous treatment, despite improved appetite and well-being. **Paradoxical progression** in the initial treatment of tuberculosis has been observed in miliary tuberculosis^{36,37}, pulmonary tuberculosis³⁸⁻⁴², pleural tuberculosis⁴³, intracranial tuberculomas^{44,45} and lymph node tuberculosis⁴⁶. The progression may be just a radiological surprise in a patient otherwise doing well⁴⁴ as in the present case, but it may be associated with symptomatic deterioration^{24,37,40-42,45}. It occurred between the second and sixth weeks^{38,40,41}, or later between the second and seventh months^{39,44} after the initiation of antituberculous treatment and is reversible with either continuation of the same chemotherapy^{40,44} or the addition of steroids^{39,42,45}. Knowledge of this type of paradoxical evolution of tuberculosis is important for the clinician as the progression might create anxiety about wrong initial diagnosis or the development of drug resistance.

Two possible mechanisms have been proposed to explain this type of paradoxical evolution. Some thought that it is a Herxheimer reaction^{39,41,47} owing to the liberation of bacillar antigens that follows the destruction by chemotherapy of tuberculous bacilli, but unlike the classical Herxheimer reaction described in the treatment of syphilis, it occurs later than 24 hours; the late reaction is attributed to the slow growth of *Mycobacteria tuberculosis* and continuing bactericidal activity of antituberculous chemotherapy⁴⁸. An alternative explanation is that it may be related to changes in the immune mechanisms^{40,49} of the patient during antituberculous treatment. An altered state of cell-mediated responsiveness has been proposed⁵⁰ for tuberculosis, similar to the spectrum of response seen in another mycobacterial infection - leprosy. It is speculated that the paradoxical reaction may be the result of altered local tissue reactivity or immunity in treated tuberculous patients⁴⁹.

A number of **haematologic abnormalities** have been described in tuberculosis, especially with disseminated disease (Table 2)^{2,5,6,12-14,30,51-66}. Various authors^{3, 59, 60} have emphasized the importance of considering disseminated tuberculosis in the presence of pancytopenia, unexplained pyrexia and weight loss. Pancytopenia attributable to hypersplenism associated with enlarged tuberculous spleen has rarely been reported⁶⁰⁻⁶². Recently, tuberculosis associated haemophagocytic syndrome has been recognized⁶³⁻⁶⁶ as a cause of pancytopenia. Both hypersplenism and haemophagocytosis are rare in miliary tuberculosis. There

is no evidence of splenomegaly nor marrow haemophagocytosis to account for the pancytopenia in our patient.

Whether miliary tuberculosis can cause pancytopenia via myelosuppressive effects has been an intriguing and controversial issue. In some cases of pancytopenia associated with miliary tuberculosis an underlying haematological disorder is evident^{51,55,56}. Glasser⁵¹ suspected that pancytopenia and leukaemoid reaction in miliary tuberculosis were due to coexisting drug toxicity or leukaemia rather than being directly due to miliary tuberculosis. Isolated case reports of patients recovering from pancytopenia have been described^{13,53-57}, but serious haematologic disorders (chronic myeloid leukaemia, myelodysplastic syndrome) subsequently developed in two cases^{55,56}. Recent studies by Maartens⁶ of 109 treated miliary tuberculosis patients in Cape Town however support the contention that miliary tuberculosis can cause reversible pancytopenia; pancytopenia occurred in 6 patients, 3 of whom recovered haematologically. This has been further supported by the demonstration of an immune-mediated mechanism of bone marrow suppression⁶⁷, and animal studies documenting the development of pancytopenia in disseminated tuberculosis involving the marrow⁶⁸.

Antituberculous drugs are known to be associated with blood dyscrasias⁶⁹, but our patient was already pancytopenic before the initiation of antituberculous chemotherapy. Macrocytosis developed in the course of his illness and his serum vitamin B12 level, initially normal, dropped to subnormal value. However, no response was seen with vitamin B12 therapy. His first bone marrow was hypocellular and hypoplastic. While on antituberculous treatment, repeat marrows were normocellular, then hypoplastic and later myelodysplastic when tuberculous

trochanteritis was diagnosed. No granulomas nor AFB were found in his marrow. Of the reported cases of disseminated tuberculosis with pancytopenia, granulomatous involvement was not invariably present; and the bone marrow could be normocellular⁶⁰, hypocellular/hypoplastic^{54,59} or myelodysplastic⁵⁷. The pancytopenia in this patient might reflect either a primary myelodysplastic syndrome, or alternatively myelodysplasia secondary to disseminated tuberculosis. Abnormal T-cell function⁷⁰ and immunological abnormalities⁷¹, including reduced immunoglobulin levels, have been reported in myelodysplastic syndrome. Reduced IgM in peripheral blood has also been reported by Sverdlava⁷² in patients with disseminated tuberculosis, especially for those with marked clinical symptoms. The immunoglobulin M level was subnormal in this patient. Our patient might have myelodysplastic syndrome with impaired immunity predisposing him to tuberculous reactivation or infection. Alternatively, the improving peripheral cell counts (Figure 3) after eradication of the tuberculous focus at the right greater trochanter might suggest that the myelodysplastic changes are secondary to the disseminated tuberculosis. It is of interest to note that a similar diagnosis of myelodysplasia secondary to disseminated tuberculosis was reported in a recent clinicopathological conference⁵⁷ of an elderly woman with pancytopenia. Nevertheless, Hunt⁵⁶ has emphasized the importance of follow-up re-examination of the bone marrow to detect persistent myelodysplasia even if the pancytopenia reversed with antituberculous treatment. Whether the myelodysplasia is primary or secondary in our case can only be settled therefore by further follow-up examination of his bone marrow.

Tuberculous trochanteritis is rare but has been reported^{73,74}. In the 30 cases reported by Franceschi⁷³, development of an abscess of the trochanteric serous bursa was a virtually constant complication and surgical excision in addition to antituberculous therapy was required in 13 cases for the advanced and aggressive forms. Radiological appearances, minimal in early forms, are currently becoming more abundant by virtue of new medical imaging techniques^{73,75}.

The caseous source for dissemination in this patient may be located in the concealed site of bone (greater trochanter in this patient), or it may be derived from reactivation of an endogenous pulmonary lesion. Slavin² observed that chronic pulmonary tuberculosis and late generalized tuberculosis coexisted far less commonly in the antituberculous chemotherapy era than they did prior to the advent of chemotherapy. The associated decline in respiratory symptoms may be the reason for the frequent misdiagnosis of miliary tuberculosis in the chemotherapy era. Slavin suspected that miliary tuberculosis in the present era is more commonly derived from caseous extrapulmonary foci, which are often clinically silent because they are located in concealed sites such as deep lymph nodes, prostate gland, bone or central nervous system. This

Table 2. Haemologic abnormalities associated with miliary tuberculosis

Anaemia — anaemia of chronic disorder
— sideroblastic anaemia
— megaloblastic anaemia: dietary folate deficiency
B12 deficiency (ileocaecal tuberculosis)
Raised ESR (may be over 100mm/hr)
Leucopenia
Thrombocytopenia
Pancytopenia — myelosuppression
— haemophagocytic syndrome
— hypersplenism
Disseminated intravascular coagulation
Polymorphonuclear leftward shift
Monocytosis
Eosinophilia
Leucocytosis
Leukaemoid reaction
Thrombocytosis

is in agreement with the opinion of Biehl²⁷ that "miliary tuberculosis not necessarily will be found in patients referred to thoracic specialists"

The **mortality** of miliary tuberculosis ranged from 24% to 100% (Table 1), being higher for those series with greater proportion of missed diagnosis. Munt¹⁴ has identified the following as adverse factors on survival: underlying non-tuberculous disease, short symptomatic history, minimal or absent temperature elevation on admission, anaemia especially a haematocrit below 29%, ease of bacteriologic diagnosis and a prompt temperature response to chemotherapy without other signs of improvement. Maartens⁶ has identified age (greater than 60 years), lymphopenia, thrombocytopenia, hypoalbuminaemia, elevated transaminase levels, and treatment delay as independent predictors of mortality. This is in accord with the few recorded survivors with miliary tuberculosis and pancytopenia.

Our patient has most of the above adverse prognostic factors and would probably have succumbed had not the therapeutic test, the appearance of miliary shadows in a repeat chest film, and the skin biopsy all pointing to the correct diagnosis, thus avoiding prolonged treatment delay.

Early diagnosis and prompt treatment are also important to prevent **occult cross-transmission** among elderly patients, as shown by a recent outbreak⁷⁶ of miliary tuberculosis. Delayed diagnosis of a case of miliary tuberculosis in a ward of 30 psychogeriatric patients resulted in an outbreak with 7 active tuberculosis and 3 tuberculosis-related deaths⁷⁶.

Although this patient presented acutely with fever and a fall, it is apparent from a retrospective detailed review of the history that he had been ill for five years. He had on-and-off malaise and had been gradually losing weight. The history of headache and suspected convulsion in 1989 might be a clue to intracerebral tuberculoma, a common cause of epilepsy in Asian countries⁷⁷. The benign thigh nodule excised in 1991 could be tuberculous, which would account for the poor healing of the excision wound. According to the patient, the skin nodules over the lower limbs have been there for two years. These skin nodules could arise by lymphatic spread from a tuberculous focus in the right greater trochanter, which remained clinically silent until the episode of fall in September 1993. The study by Slavin² suggested that multiple pathways for dissemination of tubercle bacilli exist in miliary tuberculosis, either via the lymphatics or by direct blood-stream invasion. Thus, in this patient, we think that lymphatic spread resulted in the skin nodules; while direct blood-stream invasion resulted in pulmonary and renal involvement.

*To summarize, this elderly man manifested many of the clinical and pathologic features of "cryptic" miliary tuberculosis^{1,3,5}. The **diagnoses of our patient** are:*

1. Miliary tuberculosis, with focus at the right greater

trochanteric bursa supported by radiological, operative and histological evidence; and dissemination to a) lungs evidenced radiologically, b) kidneys evidenced radiologically and bacteriologically, and c) the skin of lower limbs based on histological and bacteriological evidence. Chemotherapeutic response provides the first clinically useful evidence for tuberculosis in this patient.

2. Myelodysplastic syndrome with pancytopenia, which is either a primary haematological malignancy, or alternatively secondary to miliary tuberculosis.

Conclusions

1. Miliary tuberculosis is an important treatable condition to be considered in elderly patients presented with fever of unknown origin. Miliary tuberculosis is a diagnostic challenge. A high index of suspicion is therefore required.

2. Initial negative chest films do not exclude miliary tuberculosis. Serial chest films in the course of a fever of unknown origin are essential since miliary shadows may develop later on.

3. The presence of pancytopenia in an elderly patient with unexplained fever and weight loss should alert the physician to the possibility of cryptic miliary tuberculosis. Pancytopenia indicates poor prognosis so that prompt treatment is essential.

4. Therapeutic trial of antituberculous drugs is a valuable diagnostic method for cryptic miliary tuberculosis.

5. Failure of rapid temperature defervescence to normal should not indicate an incorrect diagnosis. A gradual decrement in temperature toward normality with improved appetite and general sense of well-being are also important indicators of improvement.

6. Paradoxical reversible radiographic progression may occur after initiating antituberculous treatment, and this should not be confused with mistaken diagnosis or the development of drug resistance.

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References

1. Sahn SA, Nelf TA. Miliary tuberculosis. *Am J Med* 1974;56:495.
2. Slavin RE, Walsh TJ, Pollack AD. Late generalized tuberculosis: a clinical pathologic analysis and comparison of 100 cases in the preantibiotic and antibiotic eras. *Medicine (Baltimore)* 1980;59:352-366.

3. Proudfoot AT, Akhtar AJ, Douglas AC, Horne NW. Miliary tuberculosis in adults. *Br Med J* 1969;2:273-6.
4. Böttiger LE, Nordenstam HH, Wester PO. Disseminated tuberculosis as a cause of fever of obscure origin. *Lancet* 1962;1:19.
5. Yu YL, Chow WH, Humphries MJ, Wong RWS, Gabriel M. Cryptic miliary tuberculosis. *QJ Med* 1986;59:421-8.
6. Maartens G, Willcox PA, Benatar SR. Miliary tuberculosis: rapid diagnosis, haematologic abnormalities, and outcome in 109 treated adults. *Am J Med* 1990;89:291-6.
7. Lei JP. Diagnostic problems in pulmonary miliary tuberculosis, an analysis of 125 cases. *Chung Hua Chieh Ho Ho Hu Hsi Tsa Chih (Chinese Journal of Tuberculosis and Respiratory Diseases)* 1990;13:214-5, 254.
8. Bobrowitz ID. Active tuberculosis undiagnosed until autopsy. *Am J Med* 1982;72:650-658.
9. Myers JA. Miliary tuberculosis in the elderly. *Br Med J* 1970;1:565.
10. Editorial: Miliary tuberculosis: A changing pattern. *Lancet* 1970;1:985-6.
11. Clinicopathologic conference: Miliary tuberculosis. *Am J Med* 1975;58:847-856.
12. Prout S, Benatar SR. Disseminated tuberculosis - a study of 62 cases. *S Afr J* 1980;58:835-42.
13. Beermann B, Engström J, Hellström K, Holm G, Lönnqvist B. Disseminated tuberculosis in elderly patients: a report on three cases diagnosed intra vitam. *Acta Med Scand* 1971;190:45-8.
14. Munt PW. Miliary tuberculosis in the chemotherapy era: with a clinical review in 69 American adults. *Medicine (Baltimore)* 1971;51:139-155.
15. Chastonay P. Late disseminated tuberculosis. Anatomoclinical correlations in 40 cases. *Rev Mal Respir* 1989;6:425-8.
16. Edlin GP. Active tuberculosis unrecognized until necropsy. *Lancet* 1978;1:650-652.
17. Yu S. Miliary tuberculosis: report of 4 cases proved by autopsy. *Chung Hua Chieh Ho Ho Hu Hsi Tsa Chih (Chinese Journal of Tuberculosis and Respiratory Diseases)* 1991;14:74-5, 125-6.
18. Ball KP, Joules H, Pagel. Acute tuberculous septicaemia with leucopenia. *Br Med J* 1951;2:869-873.
19. Ishida T, Matsumura Y, Miyake A, Yokoi T. A case of apyretic miliary tuberculosis which was discovered accidentally. *Kekkaku* 1991;66:66:493-7.
20. Petersdorf RG, Beeson PB. Fever of unexplained origin: Report on 100 cases. *Medicine (Baltimore)* 1961;40:1.
21. Berland B, Gleckman RA. Fever of unknown origin in the elderly. A sequential approach to diagnosis. *Postgrad Med* 1992;92:197-210.
22. Todd D. Pyrexia of undetermined origin. *The Hong Kong Practitioner* 1979;1(10):14-17.
23. Tandon PN. Tuberculous meningitis (cranial and spinal). In: Vinken PJ, Bruyn GW, eds. *Handbook of clinical neurology*, vol. 3, infections of the nervous system. Part I. Amsterdam: North Holland Publishing Co., 1978:195-262.
24. Maher J, Kelly P, Hughes P, Clancy L. Skin anergy and tuberculosis. *Respir Med* 1992;86:481-4.
25. Amthor M, Arents B, Bartelheimer E. Cryptococcal sepsis simulating miliary tuberculosis in malignant lymphoma. *Pneumologie* 1991;45:110-3.
26. Berger HW, Samartin TG. Miliary tuberculosis: diagnostic methods with emphasis on the chest roentgenogram. *Chest* 1970;58:586-9.
27. Biehl JP. Miliary tuberculosis. A review of sixty-eight adult patients admitted to a municipal general hospital. *Am Rev Tubercul and Pulm Dis* 1958;77:605-622.
28. Grieff M, Lisbona R. Detection of miliary tuberculosis by Ga-67 scintigraphy. *Clin Nucl Med* 1991;16:910-2.
29. Morgan MA, Horstmeier CD, De Young DR, Roberts GD. Comparison of a radiometric method (BATEC) and conventional culture media for recovery of mycobacteria from smear-negative specimens. *J Clin Microbiol* 1983;18:384-8.
30. Cucin RL, Coleman M, Eckardt JJ, Silver RT. The diagnosis of miliary tuberculosis: utility of peripheral blood abnormalities, bone marrow and liver needle biopsy. *J Chronic Dis* 1973;26:355-61.
31. Willcox PA, Potgieter PD, Bateman ED, Benatar SR. Rapid diagnosis of sputum negative miliary tuberculosis using the flexible fiberoptic bronchoscope. *Thorax* 1986;41:681-4.
32. Asenis DS, Bresciani AR. Cutaneous tuberculosis: a rare presentation of malignancy. *Clin Infect Dis* 1992;15(1):158-160.
33. Rohatgi PK, Palazzolo JV, Saini NB. Acute miliary tuberculosis of the skin in acquired immunodeficiency syndrome. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 1992;26:356-359.
34. Kong TK. Clinical audit: an elderly woman with cellulitis, subcutaneous abscesses, persistent fever and polyarthrititis. *J HK Geriatr Soc* 1993;4:30-39.
35. Wu JC, Lee SD, Yeh PF, et al. Isoniazid-rifampicin-induced hepatitis in hepatitis B carriers. *Gastroenterology* 1990;98:502-4.
36. Huseby JS, Hudson LD. Miliary tuberculosis and adult respiratory syndrome. *Ann Intern Med* 1976;85:609-11.
37. Hsu JT, Padula JP, Ryan SF. Miliary tuberculosis and respiratory distress syndrome. *Ann Intern Med* 1978;89:140-41.
38. Bobrowitz ID. Reversible roentgenographic progression in the initial treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis. *Am Rev Respir Dis* 1980;121:735-46.
39. Williams DJ, Norbert EJ, Sproude BJ. Endobronchial tuberculosis presenting as asthma. *Chest* 1988;93:836-8.
40. Muñoz Gutierrez FJ, Lazo Ramos A, Lopez Mejias J. Atypical evolution of pulmonary tuberculosis during treatment. *Chest* 1990;97:505-6.
41. Choremis CB, Padiatellis C, Zoumboulakis D, Yannakos

- D. Transitory exacerbation of fever and roentgenographic findings during treatment of tuberculosis in children. *Am Rev Respir Dis* 1980;121:735-42.
42. Chan HS, Pang JA. Effect of corticosteroids on deterioration of endobronchial tuberculosis during chemotherapy. *Chest* 1989;96:1195-6.
43. Mathay RA, Neff TA, Iseman MD. Tuberculous pleural effusions developing during chemotherapy for pulmonary tuberculosis. *Am Rev Respir Dis* 1970;109:469-72.
44. Chambers ST, Hendrickse WA, Record C, Rudge P. Paradoxical expansion of intracranial tuberculomas during chemotherapy. *Lancet* 1984;2:181-3.
45. Teoh R, Humphries MJ, Gabriel M. Symptomatic intracranial tuberculoma developing during treatment of tuberculosis: a report of 10 patients and review of the literature. *Q J Med* 1987;241:449-460.
46. Campbell IA, Dyson AI. Lymph node tuberculosis: a comparison of various methods of treatment. *Tubercle* 1971;58:171-9.
47. Ellis ME, Webb AK. Cause of death in patients admitted to hospital for pulmonary tuberculosis. *Lancet* 1983;1:665-7.
48. York EL, Norbert E, Sproule BJ. Atypical evolution of pulmonary tuberculosis during treatment. *Chest* 1990;97:505-6.
49. Editorial. Immune reactions in tuberculosis. *Lancet* 1984;2:204.
50. Lenzini L, Rotolli P, Rotolli L. The spectrum of human tuberculosis. *Clin Exp Immunol* 1977;27:230-7.
51. Glasser RM, Walker RI, Herion JC, Hill C. The significance of haematologic abnormalities in patients with tuberculosis. *Arch Intern Med* 1970;125:691-5.
52. Stein DS, Libertin CR. Disseminated intravascular coagulation in association with cavitary tuberculosis. *South Med J* 1990;83:60-3.
53. Rosenberg MJ, Rumans LW. Survival of a patient with pancytopenia and disseminated coagulation with miliary tuberculosis. *Chest* 1978;73:536-9.
54. Mangion PB. Disseminated tuberculosis complicated by pancytopenia. *Proc Roy Soc Med* 1971;64:1000.
55. Katzen H, Spagnolo V. Bone marrow necrosis from miliary tuberculosis. *JAMA* 1980;244:2438-9.
56. Hunt BJ, Andrews V, Pettingale KW. The significance of pancytopenia in miliary tuberculosis. *Postgrad Med J* 1987;63:801-4.
57. Clinicopathologic Conference: Pancytopenia and hepatosplenomegaly in a 69-year-old woman. *Am J Med* 1991;90:740-9.
58. Kalinowski SZ, Walker JM. Thrombocytopenic purpura in tuberculosis. *Brit J Tuberc* 1956;50:239.
59. Fountain JR. Blood changes associated with disseminated tuberculosis. *Br Med J* 1954;2:76-9.
60. Cooper W. Pancytopenia associated with disseminated tuberculosis. *Ann Intern Med* 1959;50:1497-1501.
61. Meredith HC, Early JQ, Becker W. Tuberculous splenomegaly with the hypersplenism syndrome. *Blood* 1949;4:13671.
62. Essop AR, Posen A, Hodgkinson JH, Segal I. Tuberculosis hepatitis: a clinical review of 96 cases. *Q J Med* 1984;212:465-477.
63. Eliopoulos G, Vaiopoulos G, Kittas C, Fessas P. Tuberculosis associated haemophagocytic syndrome complicated with severe marrow failure and disseminated intravascular coagulation. *Nouv Rev Fr Hematol* 1992;34:273-6.
64. Bellamy D, Ireland, Citron KM. Cases from King's College Hospital: A 52-year-old West Indian man with fever and a pleural effusion. *Hospital Update* 1984; Nov:889-901.
65. Weintraub M, Siegman-Ingra Y, Josiphov J, Rahmani R, Liron M. Histiocytic haemophagocytosis in miliary tuberculosis. *Arch Intern Med* 1984;144:2055-6.
66. Chandra P, Shaukat AC, Rosner F, Kagen M. Transient histiocytosis with striking phagocytosis of platelets, leukocytes, and erythrocytes. *Arch Int Med* 1975;135:989-991.
67. Bagby GC, Gilbert DN. Suppression of granulocytes by T-lymphocytes in two patients with disseminated mycobacterial infection. *Ann Intern Med* 1981;94:478-81.
68. Sabin FR, Doan CA, Forkner CE. Studies on tuberculosis. *J Exp Med* 1930; supp 13:1-152.
69. Bynoe AG, Scott CS, Ford P, Roberts BE. Decreased T helper cells in the myelodysplastic syndromes. *Br J Haemat* 1983;54:97-102.
70. CSM Update. Anti-infective drugs: adverse effects reported on yellow cards. *Br Med J* 1986;293:1163.
71. Mufti GJ, Figes A, Hamblin TJ, Oscier DG, Coplestone JA. Immunological abnormalities in myelodysplastic syndromes. *Br J Haemat* 1986;63:143-7.
72. Sverdlova MV. Immune reactivity and fibrinolysis in patients with disseminated pulmonary tuberculosis. *Probl Tuberk* 1993;1:41-3.
73. Franceschi JP, Chapuis J, Curvale G et al. Bacillary trochanteritis. Apropos of 30 cases. *Rev Rhum Mal Osteoartic* 1991;58:433-9.
74. Sovetova NA. Roentgenological manifestations of metatuberculous coxarthrosis in adults. *Ortop Travmatol Protez* 1990;5:17-24.
75. Lysikova GK, Avdrashitova DD, Akhmetov AA, Zikeev VV. Diagnostic possibilities of bone scintigraphy in osteoarticular tuberculosis. *Probl Tuberk* 1991;5:33-6.
76. Taylor DR, Allison G, Phillips DE. Tuberculosis among long term hospital residents: report of a recent outbreak. *N Z Med J* 1991;104:421-2.
77. Wadia RS, Makhale CN, Kelkar AV, Grant KB. Focal epilepsy in India with special reference to lesions showing ring or disc like enhancement on contrast computed tomography. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry* 1987;50:1298-301.